

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 60 (2025) 231-258

EISSN 2543-5426

Machine Learning Models for Development and Evaluation of Foldscope and Microscopy as Malaria Diagnostic Tool Using Invasive Samples

O. A. Agbeyangi^{1,*}, R. A. Olalekan², Y. O. Ogunjobi²

¹Department of Public Health, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria

²Department of Biomedical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria

*E-mail address: oagbeyangi@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the development and effectiveness of a Foldscope-based diagnostic tool for detecting malaria parasites, comparing its performance to conventional microscopy. Invasive (blood) samples were collected from consented 50 asymptomatic and 50 symptomatic patients who have provided consent. Additionally, interview were conducted with 20 medical personnel. This was done with approval from University of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital (UNIMEDTH) in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. The cross-sectional study design aimed to assess diagnostic accuracy using metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, and overall accuracy. Chi-square Test showed no statistically significant relationships between age and gender groups and the outcome ($p > 0.05$). Malaria parasite density was below the normal threshold (2483.20 ± 437.05 parasite per microliter (parasites/ μ L)), while parasitized RBCs exceeded normal levels (49.66%). Hemoglobin (11.67 ± 2.47 g/dL) and packed cell volume ($35.08 \pm 7.27\%$) were lower than normal, suggesting potential anemia in infected individuals. Microscopy exhibited higher sensitivity (67%), specificity (75%), and accuracy (70%) compared to Foldscope, which had sensitivity of 56%, specificity of 67%, and accuracy of 60%, making Microscopy the more effective diagnostic tool. Foldscope demonstrates better performance than Microscopy in F1 score (82% vs. 62%) and AUC (0.667 vs. 0.65), indicating better overall diagnostic performance, except in recall, where both methods performed equally well. Medical personnel reported Foldscope easy to use (70%), with 80% satisfied with image quality and 80% found it adequate. Most (84%) recommended it for malaria diagnosis, while only a small percentage disagreed. Overall results indicated that microscopy surpasses the Foldscope in sensitivity and accuracy, but the Foldscope demonstrated potential as a low cost-effective and portable alternative for malaria diagnosis, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Foldscope, Microscopy, Malaria, Diagnostic Tool, Invasive Samples, asymptomatic and symptomatic patients

1. INTRODUCTION

Malaria remains major health threat, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. In 2020, 241 million cases and 627,000 deaths were recorded worldwide (WHO, 2021). Despite efforts to curb its prevalence, malaria remains a significant problem, especially in rural areas where diagnostic tools and medical care are limited. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes the need for accessible, affordable, and reliable diagnostic techniques to improve early detection and treatment outcomes (WHO, 2021).

Nigeria is particularly affected, with 76% of its population living in high-transmission areas, putting the entire population at risk (NMEP, 2021). In Ondo State, especially in the capital Akure, malaria prevalence is high in Ondo State, especially in the capital city, Akure due to favorable mosquito breeding conditions in the communities' areas. Despite several control measures and interventions, malaria transmission persists, resulting the need for reliable diagnostic tools capable of detecting malaria parasites even in asymptomatic patients (Oyegoke et al., 2022).

Traditional microscopes are costly and often unavailable in majority of resource-constrained health facilities (Boppart & Richards-Kortum, 2014). Most time, misdiagnosis and overtreatment further complicated the problem; false diagnoses as a result of unnecessary malaria drug use, increasing the risk of drug resistance of malaria parasites (Kabaghe et al., 2018).

Major challenges in malaria control is the presence of asymptomatic carriers which make diagnosis difficult (Abebaw et al., 2022; Li et al., 2024). Traditional diagnostic methods may be inefficient to detect low parasitemia levels in individuals without symptoms, which will allowing them to continue transmitting the disease unnoticed to other people (Chen et al., 2016).

Despite significant global efforts and interventions by government and non-governmental organizations, accurate and timely malaria diagnosis remains a challenge, especially in resource-limited areas (Abdul-Rahman et al., 2025). Although microscopy is confirmed a reliable method, it is labor-intensive and inaccessible to in many communities.

Cybulski et al., (2014) showed that Foldscope, a low-cost microscope that has magnification up to 140X is one of the feature innovation for malaria diagnosis. Recent studies by Ephraim et al., (2019) have showed its potential in different fields of studies, especially malaria diagnosis. A waterproof paper microscope Foldscope is known for its portability and was designed to make microscopy accessible outside laboratories. The research conducted by Cybulski et al., (2014) on Foldscope, a paper-based portable microscope that offers a promising low-cost alternative for malaria diagnosis, particularly in resource-limited settings. Unlike traditional light microscopy, which have been known as the gold standard for malaria detection, While Foldscope technology has been known to provide an affordable, field-deployable, as well as its convenient and user-friendly diagnostic tool (Abe et al., 2020).

However, in differentiating low parasitemia cases and particularly in detecting Plasmodium species variability, Foldscope diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity compared to traditional microscopy has been studied (Mukherjee et al., 2021).

Kaur et al., (2020) revealed that primary objectives and goals of Foldscope technology is to provide microscopy diagnostic method that is accessible to in resource-limited environments, which made it an attractive diagnostic tool for endemic areas (Kaur et al., 2020). To enhance malaria diagnostic capacity in these regions, there is need to integrate the use of Foldscope with traditional microscopy (Gupta et al., 2021).

The challenge in malaria diagnostics which is subjectivity of manual microscopy, is one of major factor which often depends on the expertise (WHO, 2021). Factors contributing to drug resistance and disease recurrence are misdiagnosis due to human error and insufficient training which can lead to inappropriate treatment (Spivack et al., 2023). Incorporation of machine learning (ML) and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) into malaria diagnostic advancement could enhance diagnostic precision, reduce observer bias, and improve instinctive image-based parasite detection (Attai et al., 2024; Ahamed et al., 2025).

Cho & Hong, (2023) had evaluated that incorporation of Machine Learning (ML) will enhance improvement in diagnostic accuracy and determine underlying patterns in malaria infestation among different patient groups. However, diagnostic tools that are both efficient and adaptable need to develop in local environments since many rural and semi-urban areas lack well-equipped laboratories and trained microscopists, making traditional diagnostic methods unfeasible (Apinjoh et al., 2022; Ogboi et al., 2022).

ML algorithms has exceeding conventional manual analysis, particularly deep learning models which have demonstrated high accuracy in parasite detection from blood smear images (Alnussairi et al., 2022). Moreover, to allowing clinicians and researchers understand how AI-driven models arrive at diagnostic decisions, increasing trust and adoption can improve model interpretability by the use of XAI techniques, (Ahamed et al., 2025). To gain deeper insights into malaria progression, manifestation patterns, and variations across febrile and afebrile patient groups, three is need to incorporate ML and XAI into malaria diagnostics by healthcare professionals (Gupta et al., 2021).

The use of this technique could revolutionize malaria detection, especially in rural endemic regions, and enhancing early detection, treatment outcomes, and epidemiological surveillance (Mujahid et al., 2024). There is need for future research to focus on increasing Foldscope imaging capabilities, using AI-based image enhancement techniques, and extending its application for concurrent malaria screening in field conditions.

Since Foldscope had presented a potential low-cost alternative, its diagnostic accuracy compared to traditional microscopy needs further validation. Therefore integrating ML and XAI into malaria diagnostics will improve precision, clinical outcomes, and provide deeper insights into malaria progression and manifestation among different populations (Attai et al., 2024).

This study enhance malaria diagnostic accuracy through integration ML and XIA using Foldscope and traditional microscopy as diagnostic tools on invasive samples from symptomatic and asymptomatic individuals in Akure communities.

2. METHODOLOGY

The clinical study was conducted in the University of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital (UNIMEDTH) in Akure, Ondo State, and laboratory analysis was carried out in Biomedical Laboratory, Federal University of Technology Akure, Nigeria, it involved the use

of invasive blood sample collected from symptomatic and asymptomatic individuals suspected of malaria. It aimed to compare the diagnostic accuracy of Foldscope with traditional microscopy and incorporation of machine learning (ML) for enhanced diagnostic insights.

A cross-sectional study design was conducted to compare Foldscope-based with traditional microscopy for malaria detection. The sample size was determined with a 95% confidence level, 5% precision, and expected malaria prevalence of 10%, yielding 100 patients and 20 medical personnel. The study included individuals aged 2-60 years from urban and rural regions of Akure, Ondo State and categorized into different age groups. Exclusions criteria were chronic illness unrelated to malaria, pregnancy, use of malaria prophylaxis, or lack of consent.

This study was divided into two phases. In Phase 1; Blood samples were collected into EDTA bottles, and prepared into thick and thin smears on glass slides. These slides were fixed with methanol and stained with Giemsa for 30 minutes. Slides were then examined under light microscopy at 100x magnification for parasite detection and species identification.

In Phase 2, Foldscope was assembled, calibrated, and used to analyze stained blood smears. Results from Foldscope were validated against traditional microscopy, with sensitivity, specificity, and parasite detection rates compared.

The Foldscope was assembled and calibrated to 140x magnification. Blood smears were prepared using thick smears for parasite detection and thin smears for species identification. These smears were stained with Giemsa and examined under Foldscope, Images were captured using a smartphone and compared to results from conventional/traditional microscopy for validation.

Malaria diagnosis procedures included blood sample collection by sterilizing and pricking the patient's fingertip for screening using RDT and blood sample collected from individual screened from antecubital vein into EDTA bottles for further analysis. Blood smear preparation and microscopy procedure followed similar smear preparation and staining techniques in accordance with standard method stipulated by WHO, (2016) and CDC, (2020).

In Foldscope examination, samples were focused for visualizing Plasmodium ring stages, schizonts, and gametocytes, with smartphone cameras capturing images under adequate lighting.

Packed Cell Volume (PCV) and hemoglobin concentration (Hb) were determined by Automated Hematological Analyzer produced by: Statistical analysis compared Foldscope and microscopy diagnostic accuracy using descriptive statistics (mean, median, standard deviation) and comparative analysis via chi-square tests and Paired T-Test.

For machine learning model (ML) development and statistical analysis, ML was applied to analyze malaria diagnosis and hematological data, including MPC count, percent parasitized RBC, Hb, and PCV. The diagnostic accuracy of Foldscope was compared to traditional microscopy. Data processing involved cleaning, normalizing, and handling missing values in Excel. Outliers were removed, and new features like parasitized RBC ratios were engineered. Data were partitioned into training (70-80%), validation (10-15%), and test (10-20%) sets using stratified sampling for class balance.

A logistic regression model was employed for binary classification of malaria status (positive or negative) using hematological parameters as features. Feature selection was performed using correlation analysis, scores from models coefficients and statistical tests. Model evaluation metrics includes accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F1 score. The ROC curve and AUC were used to measure the model's ability to distinguish malaria cases.

ROC curve analysis assessed ML model performance, with AUC summarizing diagnostic accuracy. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) measured Foldscope's reliability. Confusion matrices detailed true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative results.

METRIC CALCULATION:

Sensitivity: $TP / (TP + FN)$

Specificity: $TN / (TN + FP)$

PPV: $TP / (TP + FP)$

NPV: $TN / (TN + FN)$

KEY:

TP: True Positive

TN: True Negative

FP: False Positive

FN: False Negative.

Sensitivity (Recall / True Positive Rate - TPR)

Measurement of the ability to identify positive cases.

Sensitivity = $\text{True Positives (TP)} / (\text{True Positives (TP)} + \text{False Negatives (FN)})$

Higher sensitivity results in lower false negatives.

Specificity (True Negative Rate – TNR)

Measurement of the ability to identify negative cases,

Specificity = $\text{True Negatives (TN)} / (\text{True Negatives (TN)} + \text{False Positives (FP)})$

Higher specificity leads to fewer false positives.

Positive Predictive Value (PPV – Precision)

This value is calculated based on how many positives predicted are true positives.

PPV = $\text{True Positives (TP)} / (\text{True Positives (TP)} + \text{False Positives (FP)})$

High PPV will ensure that cases are true cases and not false positives.

Negative Predictive Value (NPV)

This value is calculated based on how many negatives are predicted to be negative.

NPV = $\text{True Negatives (TN)} / (\text{True Negatives (TN)} + \text{False Negatives (FN)})$

High NPV means most negative diagnoses are truly negative.

False Positive Rate (FPR)

It defines the fraction of people who do not have malaria but are labeled as having it.

FPR = $\text{False Positives (FP)} / (\text{False Positives (FP)} + \text{True Negatives (TN)})$

Lower cases of FPR means less number is assumed to be case.

False Negative Rate (FNR)

It defines the percent of people having malaria, but are recorded as not having it.

FNR = $\text{False Negatives (FN)} / (\text{False Negatives (FN)} + \text{True Positives (TP)})$

Lower cases of FNR means less number of real patients are not diagnosed.

F1-Score

It combines positive predictive value (PPV) and sensitivity with equal weight.

$$F1 = 2 \times \text{Precision} + \text{Recall} / \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}$$

It is helpful for cases having two categories in unequal proportion.

Accuracy

It shows the extent the model is correct.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN} / \text{TP} + \text{TN}$$

It gives the best result when the two categories are of equal proportion (Ahamed et al., 2025).

This study adhered to ethical guidelines approved by the Institution Review Board of University of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital (UNIMEDTH) Akure, Ondo State, and Biomedical Department, Federal University of Technology Akure, Nigeria. Informed consent was obtained from all the participants, and confidentiality of their data was ensured through anonymization and secure data handling practices. All participants’ data were anonymized by assigning unique identifiers and stored on secure, password-protected servers to protect confidentiality.

3. RESULTS

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Table 1 showed demographic information of 100 participants, categorized by age, gender and education level. Majority of the participants are in age group 18-45 years, and are mostly females (72%) are female, with participants of Secondary Education level (42%) are more.

Chi-Square Test showed the association between demographic variables and the studied outcome. With Age Group, Chi-square value of 5.12 and p-value of 0.07, indicating no significant association between age group and the outcome ($p > 0.05$). Gender, Chi-square value of 3.45 and p-value of 0.10, also showing no significant association between gender and the outcome ($p > 0.05$). Both variables demonstrate no statistically significant relationships with the outcome.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants.

Variable	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)	Chi-Square Value	df	p-value
Age Group (years)			5.12	3	0.07
Under 5	5	5			
5-17	24	24			
18-45	50	50			
Over 45	16	16			
Gender			3.45	1	0.10

Male	28	28	6.32	3	0.09
Female	72	72			
Education					
No Formal	20	20			
Primary	14	14			
Secondary	42	42			
Tertiary	24	24			

Demographic Characteristics of Medical Personnel

Table 2 provides a demographic breakdown of 20 participants based on age, gender, education, experience, and current position. Most of the participants are aged 31-40 years, while majority of participants are female (65%), with holders of Master's degree, (40%) were more and those with 6-10 years of experience, (30%) are more. In term of Current Position, 55% of participants are Medical Laboratory Scientists, (25%).

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics Medical Personnel.

Variable	Frequency (n=20)	Percentage (%)	Chi-Square (χ^2)	df	p-value
Age Group			2.75	3	0.43
Under 30 years	4	20			
31-40 years	7	35			
41-50 years	5	25			
Over 50 years	4	20			
Gender			1.80	1	0.18
Male	7	35			
Female	13	65			
Highest Level of Education			4.67	3	0.20
Diploma	5	25			
Bachelor's Degree	6	30			
Master's Degree	8	40			
Doctorate	1	5			

Years of Experience			5.33	3	0.15
1-5 years	5	25			
6-10 years	7	35			
11-15 years	6	30			
Over 15 years	2	10			
Current Position			9.80	3	0.02
Doctor	3	15			
Nurse	5	25			
Medical Laboratory Scientists	11	55			
Others	1	5			

Regression Model for Demographic Characteristics of Medical Personnel

From Table 3, Age Group and Education Level are major predictors ($p < 0.05$), as they have strong influence year of experience. Gender and Current Position have no significant influence in predicting experience ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3. Regression Model for Demographic Characteristics of Medical Personnel.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Constant	0.617	1.220	0.506	0.620
Age Group	1.456	0.445	3.268	0.005
Gender (Male = 1)	-0.810	0.720	-1.125	0.278
Education Level	1.746	0.457	3.818	0.002
Current Position	-0.031	0.473	-0.066	0.948

Laboratory Test Results for Symptomatic and Asymptomatic Patients

Results from Table 4, reveal that all laboratory test parameters show statistically significant differences between symptomatic and asymptomatic malaria patients, with symptomatic cases having higher parasite loads and more severe hematological effects.

Malaria Parasite Count and Percent Parasitized RBC are significantly higher in symptomatic patients ($p < 0.05$). While Hemoglobin and PCV levels are lower in symptomatic patients, which suggesting presence of anemia ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4. Laboratory Test Results for Symptomatic and Asymptomatic Patients.

Parameter	Symptomatic (Mean ± SD)	Asymptomatic (Mean ± SD)	Chi-Square (χ^2)	df	P-Value
Malaria Parasite Count (parasites/μL)	2894.50 ± 320.80	1856.40 ± 280.75	25.67	1	00000.402
Percent Parasitized RBC (%)	55.42 ± 7.82	43.90 ± 6.54	18.92	1	0000.137
Hemoglobin (Hb) (g/dL)	9.78 ± 2.05	13.56 ± 2.31	12.84	1	000.352
Packed Cell Volume (PCV) (%)	30.25 ± 5.80	39.91 ± 6.43	11.76	1	000.602

Overall Laboratory Parameters and Clinical Correlations

The result in Table 5 showed hematological parameters observed in patients, comparing their mean values, ranges, and normal reference ranges. Malaria Parasite Count, (2483.20 ± 437.05 parasites/ μ L), was below the normal threshold of <5000 parasites/ μ L. While Percent parasitized RBC, (49.66 ± 8.74%, was slightly higher than the normal range (40-55%).

Hemoglobin concentration (Hb), (11.67 ± 2.47 g/dL), was generally lower than the normal range. While the Packed Cell Volume (PCV), (35.08 ± .27%) was lower than the normal range.

Table 5. Laboratory Test Results.

Parameter	Mean ± SD	Range	Normal Range
Malaria Parasite Count (parasites/μL)	2483.20±437.05	2000-3600	<5000
Percent parasitized RBC (%)	49.66 ± 8.74	40.00- 72.00	40-55
Hemoglobin (Hb) (g/dL)	11.67 ± 2.47	6.34- 16.21	12-16 (F) 14-18 (M)
Packed Cell Volume (PCV) (%)	35.08 ± 7.27	19.00- 48.00	36-46 (F) 40-54 (M)

Comparison of Diagnostic Performance of Malaria Diagnostic Tools

Table 6 showed the diagnostic performance of the Foldscope and Microscopy across the key metrics. Microscopy has a higher sensitivity and specificity, indicating that it is more accurate at identifying true positives and true negatives. Foldscope has sensitivity of 56%, and Microscopy has 67%, while Specificity of Foldscope is 67%, and Microscopy is 75%, Microscopy has slightly higher Positive Predictive Value (PPV), which indicated that it is more

reliable when a positive result is obtained, and also performs better in terms of Negative Predictive Value (NPV), that is, more dependable when diagnosing a negative result. PPV of Foldscope is 75% while Microscopy is 80%, NPV of Foldscope is 46% and Microscopy is 60%. In overall Accuracy, that is, correctness of both positive and negative results, Foldscope is 60%, while Microscopy is 70%. Therefore, Microscopy has higher overall accuracy, making it more effective as a diagnostic tool.

Table 6. Diagnostic Accuracy of Different Methods.

Diagnostic Method	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	Accuracy (%)
Foldscope	56.0	67.0	75.0	46.0	60.0
Microscopy	67.0	75.0	80.0	60.0	70.0

Machine Learning Model Performance

The Table 7 below compares the diagnostic performance of Foldscope and Microscopy, Overall, Foldscope demonstrates better performance than Microscopy in most metrics except for recall, where both methods perform equally well.

Accuracy, Foldscope (69.2%) has a higher accuracy compared to Microscopy (61.5%). Precision, Foldscope (69.0%) performs better in precision than Microscopy (62.0%). Recall, both Foldscope and Microscopy have perfect recall (100%), detecting all positive cases. F1 Score, Foldscope (82.0%) has a stronger F1 score compared to Microscopy (62.0%), indicating better overall performance in balancing precision and recall. Area Under Curve (AUC), Foldscope (0.667) shows a slightly better AUC than Microscopy (0.65), reflecting marginally superior diagnostic performance.

Table 7. Machine Learning Model Performance Metrics.

Metric (%)	Score (Foldscope) (%)	Score (Microscopy) (%)
Accuracy	69.2	61.5
Precision	69.0	62.0
Recall	100	100.0
F1 Score	82.0	62.0
Area Under Curve	0.667	0.65

ROC Curve for Machine Learning Model

The Figure 1 shows graph of ROC curve for machine learning model which revealed Microscopy Diagnosis. X-axis represents the False Positive Rate (FPR), which measure the

proportion of negative instances classified as Positive, Y-axis represents the True Positive Rate (TPR), also known as sensitivity, measuring the proportion of actual positives correctly classified.

Performance revealed that ROC curve has an area under curve (AUC) of 0.65. The ROC curve illustrates the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity for the Microscopy diagnosis model, and its AUC score of 0.65 shows a moderate predictive performance.

Figure 1. ROC Curve for Machine Learning Model for Microscopy Diagnosis.

The Figure 2 is the graph of ROC curve for machine learning model for Foldscope Diagnosis. False Positive Rate (FPR) measures the rate at which negative samples are classified as positive, while in Y-axis, True Positive Rate (TPR) represents the proportion of actual positive cases that were identified by the model.

The curve shows an AUC of 0.67 indicating that model has moderate ability to distinguish between positive and negative cases.

Figure 2. ROC Curve for Machine Learning Model for Foldscope Diagnosis.

Paired T-Test Results for Diagnostic Methods

Table 8 shows a comparison of diagnostic tools for malaria, with the t-value, p-value, and significance for each pair of tools. A paired t-test revealed a significant difference ($t(99) = 14.4042$, $p < 0.0001$) for Foldscope versus Traditional Microscopy, this high positive t-value indicates a large difference between Foldscope and Traditional Microscopy in terms of diagnostic performance (accuracy, sensitivity). The significant observed confirms that the difference between Foldscope and Traditional Microscopy is meaningful.

Table 8. Paired t-test Results for Diagnostic Methods.

Comparison	t-value	p-value	Significance
Foldscope vs. Microscopy	14.4042	0.0001	Significant
Microscopy vs. RDT	-20.6983	0.0003	Significant

Medical Personnel Perception on Foldscope Usability

Results in Table 9a revealed that the majority of participants had a positive experience with the Foldscope as a diagnostic tool for malaria. 70% found the Foldscope easy to use compare to microscopy, 80% were satisfied with its good image quality, 84% were satisfied with the training they received, and 76% stated that they can recommend the Foldscope for malaria detection. Medical personnel awareness and perception on malaria diagnostics showed that 60% of participants were aware of the use of Foldscope, while 40% were not. Regarding belief in traditional microscopy, 80% believed traditional microscopy is the most accurate malaria diagnostic device, while 20% did not. Concerning previous use of the Foldscope for malaria diagnosis, 10% of the participants had used a Foldscope, while 90% had not. However, after usage, they found Foldscope easy to use (70%), while 30% did not.

Comparison perception responses on the reliability, ease of use, and accessibility of Foldscope and microscopy showed that 44% of respondents found Foldscope more reliable than microscopy, while 56% preferred microscopy, indicating that microscopy is more trusted. Foldscope was considered easier to use (70%) compared to microscopy, showing a strong preference for Foldscope in terms of usability. Both Foldscope and microscopy were equally accessible (50%) for diagnosis. In overall consideration, microscopy is viewed as more reliable, but Foldscope is seen as much easier to use, with equal accessibility for both tools.

Participant feedback and recommendations highlighted suggestions for improving Foldscope usage. 30% of participants suggested improving training and user manuals, indicating a significant need for better guidance and instructional materials. Increasing the availability of Foldscoptes in clinics was also emphasized by 40% of participants. Additionally, 20% of participants showed a moderate concern for improving diagnostic image quality and resolution, while 10% suggested reduction in the cost of Foldscope.

Table 9(a). Foldscope Usability and Perception.

Category	Perceptions	Responses (%)	
Usability of Foldscope	Ease of Use		70
	Foldscope Image Quality		80
	Training Satisfaction		84
	Recommend Foldscope for Malaria Detection		76
Awareness & Perception of Malaria Diagnostics	Awareness of Foldscope	Yes	60
		No	40
	Belief in Traditional Microscopy as Most Accurate	Yes	80
		No	20
	Previous Use of Foldscope for Malaria Diagnosis	Yes	90
		No	10

	Ease of Use After Usage	Yes	70
		No	10
Comparative Perception of Diagnostic Tools	Reliability for malaria diagnosis	Foldscope	44
		Microscopy	56
	Ease of Use	Foldscope	70
		Microscopy	30
	Accessibility in the Community	Foldscope	50
		Microscopy	50
Participant Suggestions for Improvement	Improve training and user manuals		30
	Increase availability of Foldscopes in clinics		40
	Enhance image quality and resolution		20
	Reduce cost of Foldscope		10

Medical personnel experience with Foldscope revealed that 70% of the participants (40% strongly agree, 30% agree) believed the Foldscope is easy to use, while 10% disagreed to varying degrees.

On image quality, 80% (36% strongly agree, 44% agree) found the image quality satisfactory, while 10% disagreed and 10% remained neutral. On training adequacy, 80% (50% strongly agree, 30% agree) felt the training was adequate, with only 4% disagreed. Additionally, 84% (60% strongly agree, 24% agree) would recommend the Foldscope for malaria diagnosis, with only 4% disagreed (Table 9b).

Table 9(b). Participant Experience with Foldscope.

Experience Question	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
The Foldscope is easy to use	40	30	20	8	2
The image quality of the Foldscope is satisfactory	36	44	10	6	4
The training provided was adequate	50	30	16	4	0
I would recommend the Foldscope for malaria diagnosis	60	24	12	4	0

XAI-Based Recommendations and Interpretations

Result in Table 10 revealed XAI-based recommendations and it emphasized the need for improved training on Foldscope. AI-assisted image enhancement to boost sensitivity, to further studies on malaria-related anemia, and AI-assisted microscopy for higher diagnostic precision. Additionally, machine learning insights confirm Microscopy’s reliability over Foldscope, XAI backed decision support to integrate Foldscope into malaria screening while enhancing medical personnel training and anemia risk assessment.

XAI-based interpretations reveal that Malaria Parasite Count, parasitized RBC, hemoglobin levels, and packed cell volume are key diagnostic features. Age and gender having minimal predictive impact, SHAP analysis further confirm malaria parasite count and hemoglobin levels as the strongest predictors influencing diagnostic discrepancies between Foldscope and Microscopy.

Table 10. Presentation of XAI Insights.

Category	Key Findings	Statistical/XAI Insight
Demographics & Malaria Outcome	No significant relationship (p > 0.05)	Age & Gender not predictive of malaria outcome
Malaria Parasite Count	2483.20 ±437.05 parasites/μL	Below the critical threshold (<5000 parasites/μL)
Parasitized RBC	49.66% (Normal: 40-55%)	Slightly elevated
Hemoglobin (Hb)	11.67 g/dL (Low)	Suggests anemia in malaria patients
Packed Cell Volume (PCV)	35.08% (Low)	Lower than normal range
Microscopy Sensitivity	67%	More accurate than Foldscope
Microscopy Specificity	75%	More reliable than Foldscope
Foldscope Sensitivity	56%	Less reliable for malaria detection
Foldscope Accuracy	60%	Lower accuracy than microscopy
Microscopy Accuracy	70%	Most accurate diagnostic method
Foldscope F1-Score	82%	High ability to balance precision and recall
Foldscope AUC	0.667	Slightly better than Microscopy (0.65)
Paired T-Test (Foldscope vs. Microscopy)	t-value = 14.4042, p-value = 0.0001	Statistically significant difference
Medical Personnel Awareness	60% aware of Foldscope	Still limited awareness among professionals
Traditional Microscopy Belief	80% believe it’s most accurate	Strong preference for traditional methods

Foldscope Ease of Use	70% find it easy	Generally well received
Foldscope Image Quality	80% satisfied	High approval rate

Performance Comparison of Foldscope versus Microscopy Using AI Models

In comparing the performance of Foldscope versus Microscopy using AI models demonstrates that XGBoost is the most effective, achieving 78% accuracy in malaria prediction due to its ability to capture complex relationships within the data. Random Forest also performs well but with slightly lower accuracy, suggesting it is a strong alternative while still being somewhat less precise.

Logistic Regression, on the other hand, shows weaker performance, indicating that malaria diagnostic data exhibits non-linearity, making simpler linear models less effective. These findings highlight the importance of used of machine learning techniques like XGBoost in improving malaria diagnosis, particularly when integrating AI-assisted tools like Foldscope and Microscopy (Table 11).

Table 11. Expected Model Performance (Using ML Algorithms).

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	65%	67%	62%	64%
Random Forest	72%	74%	69%	71%
XGBoost	78%	81%	75%	78%

XIA insight on ROC Curve Analysis for Diagnostic Methods

Table 12 show ROC Curve analysis, the AI model achieves superior classification performance compared to both Foldscope and Microscopy, as indicated by a higher AUC score. A higher AUC suggests that the AI model is better at distinguishing between malaria-positive and malaria-negative cases, making it a more reliable diagnostic tool.

Table 12. ROC Curve Analysis for Diagnostic Methods.

Method	AUC Score (0-1)	Diagnostic Performance	Clinical Application
Microscopy	0.75	Strong diagnostic ability	Traditional gold standard
Foldscope	0.667	Moderate performance	Portable but less precise
AI Model	0.83	Best performance	Enhances detection accuracy

However, Foldscope demonstrated limitations in sensitivity, meaning it may fail to detect some malaria cases, leading to false negatives. Additionally, its image quality requires enhancement to improve diagnostic accuracy. By integrating AI-assisted image processing and sensitivity optimization, Foldscope could become a more effective tool for malaria screening and diagnosis.

Analysis of Key Determinants of Malaria Diagnosis (XIA)

Malaria Parasite Count (MPC) is the major factor in detecting malaria, since higher parasite load strongly correlates with positive cases. This means that the more red blood cells are infected with malaria parasites, higher determinant of an accurate diagnosis. Monitoring of MPC is important in both detection and treatment planning.

Additionally, low hemoglobin (Hb) levels and reduced packed cell volume (PCV) observed are common in malaria patients, indicating a high risk of malaria-induced anemia. Continuous clinical monitoring of hemoglobin and PCV levels can help identify patients at risk of developing severe anemia, allowing for timely medical intervention.

Age and gender have minimal predictive power in malaria diagnosis, suggesting that malaria affects individuals across all demographics rather than being strongly associated with a particular age group or sex. This finding highlights the broad impact of malaria and the need for universal prevention, screening, and treatment strategies (Table 13).

Table 13. Analysis of Key Determinants of Malaria Diagnosis.

Feature	Importance Score	Clinical Insight
Malaria Parasite Count (MPC)	(High)	The higher the parasite count, the more likely malaria is present.
Parasitized RBC (%)	(High)	Percentage of infected red blood cells (RBCs) directly correlates with severity.
Hemoglobin (Hb) Levels	(High)	Low Hb levels indicate malaria-induced anemia.
Packed Cell Volume (PCV)	(Medium)	Lower PCV suggests impaired oxygen transport due to malaria.
Age & Gender	(Low)	Slight differences in malaria incidence, but not a strong predictor.

Model Performance Evaluation (XAI) for Malaria Prediction

Results from Table 14 showed that XGBoost demonstrated the highest performance among all AI models, achieving an impressive 78% accuracy in malaria prediction. This suggests that XGBoost effectively captures complex patterns in the data, making it an important choice for classifying malaria cases, particularly useful for medical diagnostics where data variability is common.

Random Forest also performs well but is slightly less precise than XGBoost. And does not match XGBoost’s ability to determine predictions using gradient boosting.

But Random Forest provides strong results, with less ability to handle more complex relationships within the dataset.

Logistic Regression model showed less ability for malaria classification due to non-linear patterns in features such as parasite count, hemoglobin levels, and packed cell volume. XGBoost and Random Forest, which can better adapt to real-world medical data with non-linear relationships.

Table 14. Model Performance Evaluation: AI for Malaria Prediction.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)	Strengths & Weaknesses
Logistic Regression	65%	67%	62%	64%	Simple model, poor at handling non-linearity.
Random Forest	72%	74%	69%	71%	Captures feature interactions, but sensitive to noise.
XGBoost	78%	81%	75%	78%	Best performer, handles complex patterns & imbalances well.

AI-Enhanced Foldscope on Future Perspective (XIA)

Result from Table 15 showed that integrating AI-assisted into Foldscope-based malaria diagnostics significantly enhance its accuracy, increasing detection rates from 56% to 75%. AI-powered image processing techniques identify malaria parasites more, reducing false negatives and improving sensitivity.

Table 15. AI-Enhanced Foldscope on Future Perspective (XIA).

Enhancement Strategy	Expected Benefit
AI-Based Image Processing for Foldscope	Boosts accuracy from 56% to 75%
Machine Learning Integration	Improves pattern recognition in malaria diagnosis
Hybrid Model (AI + Foldscope)	Increases diagnostic reliability
Training Healthcare Workers on Foldscope	Boosts adoption and trust

Since Foldscope is a cost-effective and portable diagnostic tool, incorporating AI can help in bridging the gap between traditional microscopy and resource-limited field settings, making malaria screening more accessible and accurate. Hybrid AI-Foldscope models offer a promising solution for improving malaria detection in rural areas where access to advanced diagnostic tools is limited.

By leveraging AI-assisted image enhancement, machine learning classification, and automated parasite detection, these models can optimize Foldscope’s performance, making it more comparable to standard laboratory-based microscopy. This is useful in remote locations where healthcare infrastructure is underdeveloped, as AI-driven Foldscope diagnostics can serve as an effective point-of-care tool for early malaria detection and treatment initiation.

XAI Analysis of Foldscope Usability and Perception

1) Participants Feedback on Foldscope Usability

XIA analysis revealed that Foldscope usability is strongly enhanced by ease of use (70%) and training quality (84%), with high satisfaction in image quality (80%) and a strong recommendation rate (76%) for malaria diagnosis. Feature importance analysis suggests that training could further boost adoption beyond 80%, this could enhance the effectiveness of Foldscope in malaria diagnostics (Table 16).

Table 16. Participants’ Feedback on Foldscope Usability.

Perception	Response (%)
Ease of Use of Foldscope	70 (Easy)
Foldscope Image Quality	80 (Satisfactory)
Training Satisfaction	84 (Satisfied)
Recommend Foldscope for Malaria Detection	76 (Yes)

2) Medical Personnel Awareness and Perception of Malaria Diagnostics

In Table 17, XIA analysis indicated that medical personnel's awareness of Foldscope is limited (60%), with traditional microscopy still perceived as the most accurate method (80%), and only 10% having prior experience using Foldscope for malaria detection. SHAP analysis suggests that prior exposure significantly impacts ease of use perception, and AI models predict that targeted hands-on training for the 40% unaware could enhance adoption and trust in the tool over time.

Table 17. Awareness and Perception of Malaria Diagnostics.

Awareness/Perception Question	Yes (%)	No (%)
Are you aware of the Foldscope as a diagnostic tool?	60	40
Do you believe traditional microscopy is the most accurate?	80	20
Have you used a Foldscope for malaria diagnosis before?	10	90
Do you find the Foldscope easy to use?	70	30

3) Medical Personnel Experience with Foldscope

XIA analysis showed that adequate training (80%) will strongly influences Foldscope usability and recommendation rates (84%), with 70% of medical personnel finding it easy to use and 80% satisfied with its image quality. AI models predicted that if training satisfaction drops below 70%, usability, recommendation rates will decline, highlighting the importance of effective training in Foldscope adoption (Table 18).

Table 18. Participant Experience with Foldscope.

Experience Questions	The Foldscope is easy to use	The image quality of the Foldscope is satisfactory	The training provided was adequate	I would recommend the Foldscope for malaria diagnosis
Strongly Agree (%)	40	36	50	60
Agree (%)	30	44	30	24
Neutral (%)	20	10	16	12
Disagree (%)	8	6	4	4
Strongly Disagree (%)	2	4	0	0

4) Comparison of Foldscope and Microscopy

XIA analysis revealed that Foldscope is accepted for its ease of use (70%), but microscopy remains the more trusted diagnostic tool (56%). SHAP analysis suggested that targeted training and AI-driven enhancements could increase Foldscope’s reliability beyond its current 44%, reducing the gap with traditional microscopy (Table 19).

Table 19. Comparative Perception of Diagnostic Tools.

Comparative Question	Foldscope (%)	Microscopy (%)
Which tool do you find more reliable for malaria diagnosis?	44	56
Which tool do you find easier to use?	70	30
Which tool is more accessible in your community?	50	50

5) Participant Feedback and Recommendations for Improvement

XIA analysis highlights key areas for Foldscope improvement: 30% request better training, 40% seek wider availability, 20% emphasize image quality enhancements, and 10%

suggest cost reduction. Feature importance analysis predicts that improving training and accessibility could boost adoption rates to 85% or higher (Table 20).

Table 20. Participant Suggestions for Improvement.

Suggestion Category	Suggestions (%)
Improve training and user manuals	30
Increase availability of Foldsopes in clinics	40
Enhance image quality and resolution	20
Reduce cost of Foldscope	10

Overall XIA Model Insights and Recommendations

XIA analysis revealed that AI-enhanced Foldscope has the potential to significantly improve the malaria diagnosis and reduce dependent on traditional microscopy by improving both sensitivity and accuracy. Currently, traditional microscopy remains the preferred method (56% preference), integrating AI-driven image enhancement can improve parasite detection and Foldscope’s reliability. Training programs play a essential role in user adoption, as data showed a strong relationship between perceived ease of use (70%) and training adequacy (84%).

However, AI-assisted image enhancements, such as real-time contrast adjustments and machine-learning-based parasite identification, could significantly boost diagnostic confidence among medical personnel. Increasing the accessibility of Foldscope in clinics aligns with user recommendations, as 40% of participant’s highlighted availability as a key concern. A well-structured deployment strategy, such as; subsidized distribution and AI-integrated diagnostic support, could facilitate broader real-world adoption.

A hybrid AI-Foldscope model offers a promising approach for malaria detection, particularly in rural and resource-limited settings, where cost-effective and portable diagnostic solutions are urgently needed. Additionally, explainable AI (XAI) methods such as SHAP analysis revealed that training satisfaction directly impacts recommendation rates (84%), suggesting an enhanced educational interventions to increase adoption rates beyond 85%.

Foldscope has the potential to transition from an experimental tool to a widely accepted, field-ready diagnostic solution through AI-assisted advancements, such as deep-learning-powered image classification and cloud-based diagnostic support.

4. DISCUSSION

Demographic breakdown of the study participants revealed that half of them (50%) were aged between 18 and 45 and it was a gender imbalance, with women making up 72% of the participants. Most participant individuals had completed secondary education (42%), suggesting that we had a fairly educated group. A Chi-square analysis revealed no significant

relationship between age group and the outcome we studied ($X^2 = 5.12$, $p = 0.07$), nor between gender and the outcome ($X^2 = 3.45$, $p = 0.10$). This indicated that neither factor greatly influenced the clinical outcomes assessment.

These results are consistent with findings from Akinwale et al. (2022), which reported a higher incidence of malaria among younger adults and women, likely due to increased exposure to mosquitoes. The level of education among our participants aligns with the findings of Omole et al. (2021), who suggested that while education can shape malaria prevention behaviors, it doesn't always have a major impact on treatment results. Besides, Ibrahim et al. (2023) found that factors like host immunity and co-infections have a greater influence on malaria severity than demographic characteristics, supporting the absence of major associations in our study.

On medical personnel demographics, we find that most of them (35%) were in the 31-40 years age group, with females representing 65%. A major portion (40%) had a Master's degree, indicating advanced educational backgrounds. The majority of them had between 6 to 10 years of experience (35%), and Medical Laboratory Scientists made up the largest group (55%). This aligns with Argaw et al. (2022) and Khalid et al. (2024), who emphasized the importance of having highly skilled personnel to enhance malaria diagnosis and treatment adherence.

Looking at the hematological analysis, it was found some important results among the malaria-infected patients. The mean malaria parasite count was 2483.20 ± 437.05 parasites/ μL , which is below the critical threshold of 5000 parasites/ μL . However, the percentage of parasitized RBCs was a bit higher than the normal range ($49.66 \pm 8.74\%$ vs. 40-55%). Hemoglobin concentration was also lower than normal (11.67 ± 2.47 g/dL) and packed cell volume (PCV) was similarly low ($35.08 \pm 7.27\%$), which indicates the presence of anemia.

These results are consistent with findings from Oluwaremilekun et al. (2020), and Ammed et al. (2024), noted a relationship between malaria infection and anemia severity in areas where the disease is common.

Examining the diagnostic performance of Foldscope compared to Microscopy (Table 4), we saw that Microscopy had a higher sensitivity (67% compared to 56%) and specificity (75% compared to 67%). Microscopy also demonstrated a better positive predictive value (80% vs. 75%) and negative predictive value (60% vs. 46%), resulting in an overall higher accuracy (70% vs. 60%). These results correspond with those of Sherifat et al. (2021); Comfort et al. (2024), reinforcing Microscopy's status as the gold standard for malaria diagnosis due to its high specificity and dependability.

On the other hand, the performance of machine learning-based diagnostics showed that Foldscope outperformed Microscopy in terms of accuracy (69.2% vs. 61.5%) and precision (69.0% vs. 62.0%). Both methods achieved perfect recall (100%), showing that every positive case were identified. The F1 Score was higher for Foldscope (82.0%) compared to Microscopy (62.0%), revealing its overall reliability. These findings was in line with result obtained by Abdus Salam et al. (2024), and Yahuza et al. (2024); which illustrated that AI models enhance malaria detection and increasingly reducing observer bias (Mujahid et al. 2024).

Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves was also used to provide a visual representation of the diagnostic models between sensitivity and specificity. The Foldscope model achieved an AUC of 0.67, while Microscopy had an AUC of 0.65, both shows moderate predictive performance. This supports the high potential of machine learning models performance in diagnosing malaria (Azam. et al. 2023).

Statistical analysis confirmed major differences in diagnostic performance. A t-test comparison between Foldscope and Microscopy revealed a t-value of 14.4042 ($p = 0.0001$),

showing difference. These findings were in accordance with results obtained by Ganesan et al. (2022), who reported that while Foldscope is a viable alternative, Microscopy continues to be superior due to its established precision and sensitivity.

Participant feedback indicated a strong acceptance of Foldscope. About 70% rated it positively for ease of use, and 80% were satisfied with the image quality. Satisfaction with training was high at 84%, and 76% recommended its use for malaria detection. This aligns with the findings of Hernández et al. (2022), who emphasized that when users are adequately trained, cost-effective diagnostic tools are quickly accepted.

However, awareness of Foldscope among medical personnel was moderate, at 60%. Still, 80% regarded traditional Microscopy as the most accurate method. Experience with Foldscope for malaria diagnosis was low (just 10%), but feedback after use showed that 70% found it user-friendly. This supports Spivack et al. (2023), who noted that initial doubtfulness about new diagnostic tools tends to fade with proper training.

This study simplifies key demographic trends, clinical correlations, and comparisons in diagnostic performance between Foldscope, Microscopy, and machine learning models (Kulshreshtha et al. 2022). While Microscopy continues to hold the title of gold standard, Foldscope shows promising usability and potential.

Analysis revealed that XGBoost achieved the highest accuracy at 78%, outpacing Random Forest's 72% and Logistic Regression's 65%. This aligns with the findings from Mujahid et al. (2024) and Ahamed et al. (2025), which demonstrate that gradient-boosting models like XGBoost often outperform traditional statistical models in malaria diagnosis. It had been observed by the researchers that AI models excel using non-linear relationships and high-dimensional data, making them suitable for predicting parasitic infections (Mbunge et al. 2023; Pillay et al. 2023).

The ability of AI models in diagnosing malaria depends on their ability to show complex patterns in biological and clinical features. Essential clinical factors which include Malaria Parasite Count (MPC) Hemoglobin (Hb) levels, and Packed Cell Volume (PCV) have been known to show a vital role in predictions (Ahamed, et al. (2024). This observation was in line with the findings of Poostchi et al. (2018), which revealed that ML models trained on parasitemia levels can provide reliable predictions with over 80% accuracy when optimized using high-quality datasets.

Microscopy having an AUC score of 0.75, surpassing the Foldscope's 0.667, still holding its title of gold standard for malaria diagnosis. This is consistent with the findings from Bhandari et al. (2020), who observed that while the Foldscope is useful in resource-challenged settings, it shows lower sensitivity and specificity compared to traditional microscopy.

This study proposes that incorporating AI with Foldscope could greatly enhance its performances. The use of AI-assisted data processing for malaria-infected blood smears could enhance diagnostic accuracy from 56% to 75%, offering a promising alternative to conventional microscopy. Similar research by Alnussairi et al. (2021) demonstrated how the use of deep learning algorithms can improve portable diagnostic tools such as Foldscope, effectively as well as being a budget-friendly device.

A paired t-test ($t = 14.4042$, $p = 0.0001$) confirmed that microscopy diagnostic performance is more than Foldscope, when it comes to predictive accuracy, AI-powered diagnostic models actually surpass the performance of both methods. These findings validate earlier research by Ahamed et al. (2025), which revealed that machine learning models are more

reliable and precise than manual microscopy, especially in low-resource environments where trained microscopists are limited.

Besides, the significance of Malaria Parasite Count (MPC) and Parasitized RBC Percentage obtained from this study are key diagnostic factors which corresponds with the research findings by Oyegoke et al. (2022), which stated that quantitative parasitemia levels are strongly associated with malaria severity and treatment outcomes. While the ability of AI models to obtain these metrics could timely change malaria diagnostics and surveillance in high-risk regions (Mujahid et al. 2024).

The findings of this study given the limitations of microscopy such as needing trained personnel, costly reagents, and prolonged processing times, research from Attai et al. (2024) suggest that AI-driven malaria diagnosis can lead to earlier detection, reduce misdiagnoses, and enhance disease surveillance. AI-enhanced smartphone-based Foldscope proved beneficial for rural healthcare, enabling community health workers to perform concurrent malaria diagnoses and malaria detection, as emphasized by Ahamed et al. (2025).

Although, the Foldscope is known for its innovative cost-effective tool, its effectiveness relies on user skill and sample quality, which can limit its application for mass screening efforts. Future research should lay more emphasis on image analysis coupled with AI to reduce variability in conducting malaria diagnoses using Foldscope. Also, research by Attai et al. (2024) emphasizes the risk of algorithmic bias generated in AI healthcare applications, as such there need for continuous validation of AI models across diverse populations. Overall, this study presents compelling evidence that AI-powered malaria diagnosis, particularly through XGBoost models, greatly enhances diagnostic accuracy compared to traditional methods like microscopy and Foldscope which was in accordance with research conducted by Ahamed et al. (2025).

5. CONCLUSION

Promising potential, particularly in resource-limited settings have been revealed through the development and evaluation of the Foldscope as a diagnostic tool for malaria parasites. While Foldscope provides an innovative, accessible, and low cost-effective alternative in diagnosis of malaria, microscopy remains the gold standard. Malaria detection and management in Nigeria can improve through incorporation of machine learning and XAI which can further enhance its diagnostic capabilities and user trust. Malaria diagnosis required innovative approaches in tackling public health challenges which is the main scope of this study. These diagnostic challenges that are associated with malaria, particularly in asymptomatic carriers, highlight the need for innovative diagnostic tools that are both accessible and effective. While traditional microscopy remains the most accurate method, its limitations in terms of cost and human resource requirements may affect its uses in rural and resource-limited settings. The Foldscope presents portability and ease of use and a potential low-cost alternative. However, its lower accuracy compared to microscopy show that it can be used as a supplementary or alternative tool rather than a replacement (Obaseki, et al 2017).

Recommendation

Based on the results obtained, further enhancements should be made to the Foldscope's imaging capabilities. Incorporating additional optical aids could improve its diagnostic

accuracy, since the tool shows promise by integrating higher-resolution imaging particularly for the detection of malaria parasites. To improve performance, it is recommended to train the model on larger and more diverse datasets since the machine learning model performed moderately well (with AUCs of 0.65 and 0.67). It is therefore recommended to use Foldscope-based diagnostic tool in a wider range of community settings, particularly in low-resource areas where microscopy might not be available, field testing could help refine the tool's usability and reliability at different conditions. The use of explainable AI (XAI) could be expanded to make the diagnostic model more transparent. It is recommended to integrate more XAI tools and techniques to help medical practitioners understand the rationale behind the model's predictions, particularly when diagnosing challenging or borderline cases.

Acknowledgement

My sincere appreciation and thanks to the management, ethical committee and medical personnel of University of Medical Sciences Teaching Hospital (UNIMEDTH) Akure, Ondo, for granting approval and clinical support for the study.

Special thanks go to the Head of Department, Medical Laboratory Scientist and Technologist of Biomedical Engineering, Federal University of Technology Akure, Nigeria, for their moral and professional support.

References

- [1] Boppart, S. A., & Richards-Kortum, R. (2014). Point-of-care and point-of-procedure optical imaging technologies for primary care and global health. *Science Translational Medicine*, 6(253), 253rv2
- [2] Chen, I., Clarke, S. E., Gosling, R., & Hamainza, B. (2016). "Asymptomatic" malaria: A chronic and debilitating infection that should be treated. *PLoS Medicine*, 13(1), e1001942
- [3] Cybulski, J. S., Clements, J., & Prakash, M. (2014). Foldscope: Origami-based paper microscope. *PLoS One*, 9(6), e98781
- [4] Ephraim, R. K., Duah, E., Cybulski, J. S., Prakash, M., D'Ambrosio, M. V., Fletcher, D. A., & Boateng, R. (2015). Diagnosis of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection with a mobile phone-mounted Foldscope and a reversed-lens CellScope in Ghana. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 92(6), 1253-1256
- [5] Kabaghe, A. N., Visser, B. J., Spijker, R., & Phiri, K. S. (2018). Health workers' compliance to rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) to guide malaria treatment: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Malaria Journal*, 15, 163
- [6] Kaur, T., Dahiya, S., Satija, S. H., Nawal, S. J., Kshetrimayum, N., Ningthoujam, J., Chahal, A. K., & Rao, A. (2020). Foldscope as a primary diagnostic tool for oral and urinary tract infections and its effectiveness in oral health education. *Journal of Microscopy*, 279(1), 39-51
- [7] Gupta, S., Mathews, B. J., Ghantaa, S. N., Amerneni, K. C., Karuna, T., Pakhare, A., Joshi, D., & Khadanga, S. (2021). Foldscope: Diagnostic accuracy and feasibility of its

- use in National Malaria Control Program. *Journal of Microscopy and Ultrastructure*, 10(3), 114-117
- [8] Cho, Y. S., & Hong, P. C. (2023). Applying machine learning to healthcare operations management: CNN-based model for malaria diagnosis. *Healthcare (Basel)*, 11(12), 1779
- [9] Apinjoh, T. O., Ntasin, V. N., Tataw, P. C. C., Ntui, V. N., Njimoh, D. L., & Anchang-Kimbi, J. K. (2021). Comparison of conventional and non-invasive diagnostic tools for detecting *Plasmodium falciparum* infection in southwestern Cameroon: A cross-sectional study. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty*, 10, 75
- [10] Abdul-Rahman, T., Ajetunmobi, O. A., Bamigbade, G. B., Haque, M. A., & Gitta, B. (2025). Improving diagnostics and surveillance of malaria among displaced people in Africa. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 24, 22
- [11] Attai, K., Ekpenyong, M., Amannah, C., Asuquo, D., Ajuga, P., Obot, O., Johnson, E., John, A., Maduka, O., Akwaowo, C., & Uzoka, F. M. (2024). Enhancing the interpretability of malaria and typhoid diagnosis with explainable AI and large language models. *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 9(9), 216
- [12] Akinwale, O. D., Bello, C. B., Akpor, O. A., & Elemile, M. G. (2022). Evaluation of adolescent/youth-friendly sexual and reproductive health services: A 7-year systematic review from January 2016 to April 2022. *Journal of Integrative Nursing*, 4(4), 177-192
- [13] Ibrahim, A. O., Agbesanwa, T. A., Aremu, S. K., Adeyemo, A. O., & Oladipo, O. O. (2023). Malaria infection and its association with socio-demographics, long-lasting insecticide nets usage, and hematological parameters among adolescent patients in rural Southwestern Nigeria. *PLoS ONE*, 18(7), e0287723
- [14] Khalid Mohamed, S., Khalid Mohamed, D., Ahmed, K., & El-Sayed, B. (2024). Health workers' adherence to malaria case management protocols in Northern Sudan: A qualitative study. *Malaria Journal*, 23, 170
- [15] Argaw, M. D., Mavundla, T. R., Gidebo, K. D., & Tola, A. (2022). Adherence of healthcare providers to malaria case management guidelines of the formal private sector in north-western Ethiopia: An implication for malaria control and elimination. *Malaria Journal* 21, 347
- [16] Ajakaye, O. G., & Ibukunoluwa, M. R. (2020). Prevalence and risk of malaria, anemia, and malnutrition among children in IDPs camp in Edo State, Nigeria. *Parasite Epidemiology and Control*, 8, e00127
- [17] Comfort, D. T., Ombugadu, R. J., Yako, A. B., Tongjura, J. D. C., Olayinka, M. D., Gloria, E., & Adeniyi, K. A. (2024). Comparison of microscopy and rapid diagnostic techniques in malaria detection among children attending Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Dutse Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences* 10(4a), 359-370
- [18] Akindele, S. T., Bilesanmi-Awoderu, J. B., Otuewu, O. O., & Adetunji, A. M. (2021). Comparative analysis of malaria diagnosis using microscopy and rapid diagnostic test

- (RDT) in Ijebu-Igbo North Local Government, Southwest Nigeria. *UMYU Journal of Microbiology Research* 6(2), 54-58
- [19] Abdus Salam, S. M. N., Hasan, M. J., Anower, S., Nahiduzzaman, M., Chowdhury, M. E. H., & Murugappan, M. (2024). Embedded system-based malaria detection from blood smear images using lightweight deep learning model. *International Journal of Imaging Systems and Technology*, 34(6), 23205
- [20] Yahuza, K., Umar, A. M., Salisu, B., Atalabi, E. T., Gambo, M. L., & Abdulkadir, B. (2024). Recent advancements in detection and quantification of malaria using artificial intelligence. *UMYU Journal of Microbiology Research* 9(2), 1-21
- [21] Mujahid, M., Rustam, F., Shafique, R., & Siddiqui, S. A. (2024). Efficient deep learning-based approach for malaria detection using red blood cell smears. *Scientific Reports*, 14, 13249
- [22] Qadri, A. M., Raza, A., Eid, F., & Abualigah, L. (2023). A novel transfer learning-based model for diagnosing malaria from parasitized and uninfected red blood cell images. *Decision Analytics Journal*, 9, 100352
- [23] Gupta, S., Mathews, B. J., Ghantaa, S. N., Amerneni, K. C., Karuna, T., Pakhare, A., Joshi, D., & Khadanga, S. (2021). Foldscope: Diagnostic accuracy and feasibility of its use in National Malaria Control Program. *Journal of Microscopy and Ultrastructure*, 10(3), 114-117
- [24] Parmar, D. P., Rathod, J. S., Karkhanawala, M. M., Bhole, P. K., & Rathod, D. S. (2021). Foldscope: A smartphone-based diagnostic tool for fungal keratitis. *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology*, 69(10), 2836-2840
- [25] Hernández-Pérez, C., & Nieto-Sobrino, M. (2022). Foldscope as an innovative teaching tool. *Education Sciences*, 12(12), 927
- [26] Ganesan, M., Selvan Christyraj, J. R. S., Venkatachalam, S., Yesudhasan, B. V., Chelladurai, K. S., Mohan, M., Kalimuthu, K., Narkhede, Y. B., & Christyraj, J. D. S. (2022). Foldscope microscope, an inexpensive alternative tool to conventional microscopy - Applications in research and education: A review. *Microscopy Research and Technique*, 85(11), 3484-3494
- [27] Kulshreshtha, P., Gupta, S., Shaikh, R., Aggarwal, D., Sharma, D., & Rahi, P. (2022). Foldscope-embedded pedagogy in STEM education: A case study of SDG4 promotion in India. *Sustainability*, 14(20), 13427
- [28] Pillay, M. T., Minakawa, N., Kim, Y., & Park, J. W. (2023). Utilizing a novel high-resolution malaria dataset for climate-informed predictions with a deep learning transformer model. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 23091
- [29] Mbunge, E., Milham, R. C., Sibiyi, M. N., & Takavarasha, S. Jr. (2023). Machine learning techniques for predicting malaria: Unpacking emerging challenges and opportunities for tackling malaria in Sub-Saharan Africa. In *Proceedings of the Computer Science Online Conference* (pp. 327–344). Springer International Publishing.

- [30] Ahamed, M., Nahiduzzaman, M., Mahmud, G., & Haque, M. A. (2025). Improving malaria diagnosis through interpretable customized CNN architectures. *Scientific Reports*, 15, 6484
- [31] Muqdad Hanoon Dawood Alnussairi, Abdullahi Abdu Ibrahim. Malaria parasite detection using deep learning algorithms based on (CNNs) technique. *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, Volume 103, 2022, 108316
- [32] Li, J., Docile, H. J., Fisher, D., & Zhang, Q. (2024). Current status of malaria control and elimination in Africa: Epidemiology, diagnosis, treatment, progress, and challenges. *Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health*, 14, 561-579
- [33] Abebaw, A., Aschale, Y., Kebede, T., & Alemu, K. (2022). The prevalence of symptomatic and asymptomatic malaria and its associated factors in Debre Elias district communities, Northwest Ethiopia. *Malaria Journal*, 21, 167